

Climate Action at the Intersection of Feminism and Craft Practice: Developing a Theoretical Framework for a Regenerative Textile Design Pedagogy

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Abstract

Textile Design and other fields that fall under the umbrella of 'craft practice' are relatively new to academic study, due to the association of craft with women, marginalized, and Indigenous communities. Because of this, Textile Design is an ideal ground to explore experimental and critical pedagogy and emerging ideas of climate action and justice to respond to student needs. The innate connection to material core to textile practice and the role of the textile and fashion industries in the current environmental crisis create an undeniable requirement for sustainable literacy, and for a higher education pedagogy that engages with the reality of climate change. Building on established and emerging design frameworks such as Transition Design, Regenerative Design, Intersectionality and Eco-Feminism, we begin to co-develop a framework for curriculum with student-stakeholders which links the practices, livelihoods, and lived experience of women to the issues facing the climate and prepares them with the necessary tools and mindsets for their futures.

Keywords: Climate action, intersectionality, pedagogy, regenerative design, textile design.

1. Introduction

For many years, lively debate has persisted regarding the relevance or suitability of Textiles as a field of academic study; however, the contemporary definition of Textiles is now something even more complex and nuanced than the traditional craft disciplines it has grown from (Gale and Kaur 2002; Adamson 2010). The scope of creative processes found in Textile practice defy the historical divisions and definitions applied to it; these contradictions instead contribute to its manifold nature and simultaneously diverge into both craft and towards technology (Gale and Kaur 2002). Traditionally, textiles¹ provide warmth and protection, help us identify with each other, signal social status, and form a vital part of ritual and cultural practice. Textiles are inextricably linked with humans and have played key roles in human and cultural development since the first piece of string was plied in the Stone Age (Barber 1995). The textile industry has played a fundamental role in shaping the global political and economic landscape more than any other sector – with ties and roots in the colonialist movement, the Transatlantic slave trade, and the Industrial Revolution to name a few (Barber 1995; Gale and Kaur 2002). In contemporary culture, novel textile designs, fabrication and development, and creation of seasonal textile trends play key roles in the development of a booming industry and have heavily influenced consumer behaviour and mindsets (Gale and Kaur 2002). It's hard to find a part of human history or human experience not coloured by contact with textiles or the textile industry.

“Textiles are in the very grain of what we are – as we respond, so they respond, as we change, so they change. Because Textiles are so implicated in what we are, as an industry it has had the power to influence human destiny through social and political structures.” (Gale and Kaur 2002)

Despite the magnitude of their global impact and role in shaping human history, craft practices and tacit craft knowledge passed down intergenerationally are often not granted the same respect in academic circles as the research and practice of either fine art or design (Adamson 2010; Igoe 2021). Whether this is because craft is often the practice of indigenous peoples, communities of colour, or women is grounds for additional debate; the result remains that craft and those fields that have historically fallen under the umbrella of craft practice such as Textiles are still relatively new to comprehensive and legitimate academic study (Adamson 2010). Because of this relatively untread path, Textile practitioners and academics are not fighting entrenched preconceptions, long-established ways of working within higher education, or established routes from research methodologies to pedagogy. Critical evaluations of the Textile design process and the industry itself are few and infrequently published, and most current papers and research merely illustrate the areas in which Textile design activity is taking place across a range of industries, instead of articulating or defining what the process entails for Textile designers (Igoe 2021). Thus ‘Textile design’ in many ways still needs defining, and through working at this definition we can begin to shape more fully the methods for Textile design thinking and practice and scope out a pedagogy for the study of Textiles within higher education.

The connection to material that has always been core to Textile practice creates an undeniable requirement for sustainable material understanding and the need for this to reflect into the teaching of Textile practice in Higher Education (Barber 1995; Igoe 2021). Additionally, due to the role the Textile industry has had in contributing to the current environmental crisis, sustainable knowledge, capabilities, and literacy will be key requirements for the next generation of Textile designers as they enter an industry required to shift patterns of consumption and production to survive (Gale and Kaur 2002). Due to lengthy supply chains and energy-intensive manufacturing methods, the textile industry generates 8–10% of global carbon emissions, superseding emissions from the aviation and shipping industries combined; up to 20% of global industrial wastewater pollution is caused by textile

dyeing and finishing; and the textile industry generates roughly 1.2 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalent, or nearly 10% of world GHG emissions each year (European Parliament 2021; Morlet 2017; UNFCCC 2018).

Global fibre production almost doubled between 2010–2020 (from 58 million to 109 million tons) and shows no sign of slowing as global demand for fashion continues to grow (Textile Exchange 2021; Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2017).

Higher education must also confront climate anxiety, which should be considered in shaping a future pedagogy that supports and responds to the needs of student-stakeholders. The phrase climate or eco-anxiety has risen to prominence in the last decade to loosely describe worries owed to a changing climate, and research is showing that these feelings are becoming increasingly common (Tsui 2024). The Climate Psychological Alliance more broadly defines “eco-anxiety” as heightened emotional, mental, or somatic distress in response to dangerous changes in the climate system (Clayton 2017). These feelings of stress and distress are especially prevalent in young people, who often express dismay at inheriting an unstable future, and have lived under the looming spectre of climate disaster their entire lives (Bednarek 2024). A recent global study, which surveyed 10 000 young people from 10 countries, showed that nearly 60% of them were extremely worried about the future state of the planet (Hickman et al. 2021). Nearly half said that this distress affected them daily and three-fourths agreed with the statement “the future is frightening” (Hickman et al. 2021; Hossain 2022). Similar research investigating the impact of climate change on 10 000 university students in 32 countries found that it was impacting young people across the globe, with a quarter of respondents saying they felt “terrified” about climate change (Ogunbode 2022). A February 2022 IPCC assessment was the first to mention how temperature increase, trauma from extreme events, and the loss of livelihood due to climate can negatively influence mental health, noting that young people, older adults, and those with pre-existing health conditions are the most vulnerable (IPCC 2022). And at a 2022 United Nations conference in Stockholm, the World Health Organization released a new policy brief that discussed how climate change poses serious risks to people’s mental health (World Health Organization 2022).

Image 1: Youth protest at COP28 during the final day of negotiations. Credit: Jennifer Drantlet

Thus, any relevant education for young people must hold space for and acknowledge the constant toll on mental health from their environment, and how living under the shadow of this crisis shapes their worldview (Tsui 2024; Bednarek 2024). While it might be scary and seem counter-intuitive to many educators, a future-fit pedagogy must introduce and embrace themes of Climate Action and Justice to empower students in the roles they can and must take up in their

¹ It should be noted that in this text, “Textiles” is not used interchangeably with cloth; the term in this article will be used to describe the entire gamut of textile applications.

futures (Tsui 2024; Bednarek 2024; Servant-Miklos 2024). These conversations create safe and supported spaces for processing grief alongside educators and encourages students to feel a sense of agency to take forward action (Bednarek; Servant-Miklos 2024). Enabling space for this conversation within education is a vital tenant of a proposed framework, and a direct response to the global context the framework sits within. Pedagogy must be contextually defined, and it must respond specifically to the conditions, formations, and problems that arise in the sites where education takes place (hooks 1994). Rather than treating pedagogy as a commodity, progressive educators need to engage with their teaching as a theoretical resource that is both shaped by- and responsive- to the very problems

that arise between the spaces, places, and contexts that connect classrooms with the experience of everyday life (hooks 1994; Freire 1970).

In this vein, situating a Textile design curriculum within higher education in 2025 (and beyond) must address the social and environmental impacts of the textile industry, the required changes to industry and mindsets, and the impact of all social, political, and environmental factors on the students navigating the educational system. The nature of Textile thinking and Textile practice is to be both of its time and situated in a specific place, and so must a Textile design pedagogy be (Gale and Kaur 2002).

2. Existing Design and Pedagogical Frameworks

The following frameworks have been selected as relevant to Textile thinking and textile practice, and their values and methods can be viewed as Feminist. The implied (and at times explicit) link between craft practice, textile tacit knowledge, and the sphere of women's work makes a Feminist praxis a relevant sorting and selection metric. These selected frameworks are considered and discussed, and a resulting amalgamation is defined and proposed as a future methodology of Regenerative textile design practice and pedagogy². The following is not intended to be an exhaustive list of influential frameworks and theories, as environmental theories often build on, borrow from, and intertwine with other related areas.

2.1. Eco-Feminism/ Feminism and Ecology

The term 'the Feminist Movement' can be used broadly to define a series of global struggles to uplift the plight of women, seek political, economic, personal, and social equality of the sexes, and put an end to sexism and gender discrimination (Mellor 1997). This movement can be divided into four waves, each of which seeks to tackle gender disparities and experiences in increasing detail. The first wave addressed the fight for women's suffrage (late 19th century), whereas the current 4th wave movement (2010s- present) is defined by more nuanced and contemporary discussions of issues facing women, such as body positivity, challenging rape culture, advocating for trans rights, and applying intersectionality (Munro 2013).

The second wave of Feminism, after women's right to vote was widely achieved by the early 20th century, co-emerged with both the burgeoning American civil rights and environmental/Earth Day movements in the 1960s-1980s (Munro 2013). This wave of feminist action, research, and scholarship sought to explore societal gender norms, women's roles in society, and deeply entrenched biases around womanhood. Feminists at this time began to push back about women's roles, even while many reclaimed postures and attitudes of femininity. One defining characteristic of this wave of Feminism is an overlap with the Environmental movement, which led many activists to define and quantify our relationship to the Earth through a lens of motherhood. Many slogans for the first Earth Day (22 April 1970) referred to "Mother Earth", which was also a sentiment shared in the emerging Gaia Theory, which identified the interconnected and nurturing nature of planetary systems (Lovelock 1972). Women's bodies and menstrual cycles, as well as typically 'feminine' acts of care, were seen to correspond to natural cycles of birth, growth, decay, and regeneration and the overarching ebb and flow of the planet itself (hooks 1994; Thomas 2022).

Codifying this link and building on the foundation of Feminist second wave thought, Ecofeminism is a philosophy and movement that identifies the dual oppressions of both women and the environment as rooted in patriarchal structures (Mellor 1997). It is a movement that sees a connection between the exploitation and degradation of the natural world and the subordination and oppression of women (Mellor 1997). Both women and the planet are assigned value through their ability to please and serve men – particularly white men – and to reinforce the pervasive economic system of capitalism (Tsui 2024;

Thomas 2022). Ecofeminism also seeks to highlight voices that have been historically ignored, and vulnerable populations that have been violated and oppressed. Ecofeminists propose that if we're not aware of the patterns that rule our society, we are inclined to repeat the same injustices and will not tackle the climate crisis at its root. We cannot ignore the role of patriarchy, racism, and other injustices if we hope to have effective climate action and justice (Tsui 2024, 108).

Historically, women have become associated with textile production and craft because through childbirth and childcare, women needed to take up categories of work appropriate to the domestic environment. (Gale and Kaur 2022). Such arguments are often developed further to suggest that women through their nature are adept at building community, and textiles manufacture generally requires a fixed location and a variety of activities (Gale and Kaur 2022). After Feminism, many women see the idea of gender-specific proclivities as a purely social construct, so the repeated dismissal of the innate creative stature of women becomes rooted in patriarchal biases. Decorative arts and crafts are granted less respect than other creative practices- by default a reassertion of women's rank in the arts (Gale and Kaur 2022). Canons of Art History have perpetuated myths of 'the great white male artist', which further establishes a hierarchy that favours oil paintings over crafts and textiles. This exposes the systemic sexism within Art History and how women's contributions were often ignored or negated (Parker and Pollock 1981). Even within Feminist circles, decorative textiles are either valorized or dismissed, as they are often felt to lean too closely into male articulations of female talents (Parker and Pollock 1981; Parker 1984).

Textile design is a gendered academic subject within the UK with a significant majority-female cohort at higher education. This gender divide not only leads to imbalance within the workforce but perpetuates the stereotype of textile production as unpaid domestic labour (Coulter 2023; Bell 2013).

The explanation of why in many developed modern societies more women than men undertake textile education is not straightforward. Certainly, there is no universal acceptance of preference based on gender so we must presume it's a social construction, a familiar and accepted belief about the talents and roles of women. We might equally presume that men have been encouraged to have negative perceptions about the practice of textiles. There are undoubtedly a range of sociological and Feminist answers to the subject and gender divide, but there remain some more difficult questions around issues such as femininity (and masculinity) and textiles, which by and large remain unstudied to this day (Gale and Kaur 2022).

As Textile design education was initially born out of a tacit craft practice, skills in 'making' and practical techniques were passed down from one generation of students to the next, however the intention and 'why' of the work was rarely questioned (Gale and Kaur 2002; Igoe 2021). This was reinforcing the old stereotypes around the value of women's work, and of craft heritage, and also codified the perception of Textiles as a decorative or constructive realm that existed to create

² It should also be clarified that while theoretical development by a man is not an exclusionary criterion, most of the selected frameworks (in addition to being Feminist) are the scholarly work of women, as is the proposed framework. In the spirit of intersectionality, we have selected theories developed by women to highlight and amplify their work, and for their relevance to application within a female-dominated industry and HE sector.

textile products, fabrics, or embellishments to be added to the more important and considered work of others (typically men- architects, product designers or fashion designers) (Parker and Pollock 1981; Parker 1984). Adopting a Feminist lens with which to view textile design enables a critical position that challenges current extractive and unjust systems of design and women's role within them (Lean 2021).

2.2. Transition Design

Transition design is a still-developing field of research and inquiry, and as such has enormous potential to be applied across many disciplines of design, including Textile design. Professor Terry Irwin developed the field of Transition design in 2015 to create a rich, multi-disciplinary approach to solving the world's 'wicked problems' by building on the influential writings of Wolfgang Sachs, Victor Papanek, and more (Irwin 2015; Sachs 1992; Papanek 1995). Transition design theory proposes that the problems facing humanity, and the problems we are already embroiled in, are interconnected, interdependent and always manifest in place and culture-specific ways. Transition design argues that new knowledge and skill sets are required to address these problems, and that their resolution is a strategy for igniting positive, systems-level change and societal transitions toward more sustainable, equitable and desirable long-term futures (Irwin 2015). Transition design uses multiple levels of analysis and knowledge to identify actionable steps toward sustainability and systemic health. Drawing on multiple fields and disciplines, transition design allows a rich, multi-faceted consideration of problems and opportunities for systems intervention.

"Transition design acknowledges that we are living in 'transitional times'. It takes as its central premise the need for societal transitions to more sustainable futures and argues that design has a key role to play in these transitions. It applies an understanding of the interconnectedness of social, economic, political and natural systems to address problems at all levels of spatiotemporal scale in ways that improve quality of life." (Irwin 2015)

Transition design is still in the first phases of practice and application, so many of the initial case studies are still in progress due to long-term futuring. However, Irwin has defined pinpoints of transition design theory and a system of engaging stakeholders through participatory workshops, and these can be adapted and selected to further develop our own framework. Pinpoints of transition design theory can be grouped into three areas of inquiry and intervention: technical, environmental, and cultural. These pinpoints, such as Living Systems Theory, Futuring, Indigenous Wisdom, Cosmopolitan Localism, Everyday Life Discourse, Post-normal Science, Needs and Social Practice Theory, and Alternative Economics help to inform the web of stakeholders inputting into future visions, lending their voice and expertise, and also offer fertile areas of practice to inspire system changes (Irwin 2015; Irwin 2019).

Transition design's acknowledgement of the cultural role of materials and practices in both systemic issues and as a potential site of system healing makes this a relevant framework for application within Textiles, whose connection to human culture and history cannot be divested (Barber 1995; Irwin 2015). As well, the focus on employing and engaging with a wider net of stakeholders and experts in framing both problems and solutions can be seen as a feminist and intersectional praxis, making this theory a valuable contributor to the proposed pedagogy.

2.3. Intersectional Environmentalism

In the early 1990s, civil rights advocate and critical race scholar Kimberlé Crenshaw articulated the theory of intersectionality, which can be defined as the complex and cumulative way in which the effects of multiple forms of discrimination (such as racism, sexism, and classism) combine, overlap, or intersect, especially in the experiences of marginalized individuals or groups (Crenshaw 1991; Thomas 2022). This theory was born out of the American civil rights movement of the 1960s, and the concurrent and subsequent waves of Feminism in America, which often did not include and properly acknowledge the voices and experiences of black women. Crenshaw and other scholars

of the intersectional feminist movement defined the mechanisms through which they were often marginalized and ignored even within fights for liberation and justice, despite suffering from multiple axes of oppression (Crenshaw 1991).

The theory of intersectionality can also be applied to the emerging climate crisis, as the same systems of oppression that impact people also degrade the planet (Thomas 2022; Tsui 2024). Intersectional environmentalism is an inclusive approach to environmentalism that advocates for the protection of both people and the planet. It argues that social and environmental justice are intertwined and that environmental actions that disregard this connection are harmful and incomplete and focuses on achieving climate justice by amplifying historically excluded voices and approaching environmental education, policy, and activism with equity, inclusion, and restorative justice in mind (Thomas 2022). People of colour, women, and marginalized communities around the world are bearing the brunt of the climate crisis and environmental injustice (Thomas 2022). Black, Brown, Indigenous, and impoverished people and countries of the Global South – countries that are moving toward becoming industrial and often have a history of colonialism – are facing environmental injustice at alarming rates (Thomas 2022; IPCC 2022). In other words, those least responsible for the climate crisis are bearing the worst impacts of it (IPCC 2022).

Beyond just championing the voices of all stakeholders and everyday citizens, intersectional environmentalism states that traditionally marginalized and oppressed communities such as Indigenous people, people of colour, women, and the economically disadvantaged must actively be at the forefront of any movements for environmental and climate justice (Thomas 2022). Women make up nearly 80% of the textile garment workforce globally, and women's fashion accounts for over 53% of global fashion retail spending, meaning women are a majority in both the workforce and customer base for the textile industry, while holding only 20% of leadership positions within the fashion and textile industries (Labour Behind the Label, no date; FashionUnited, no date; Iglesias 2025). A report by Employment Studies shows that 94% of graduates of fashion and textile design courses are female, and of UK interior design students (a related design discipline), 83% were female (Ball 2010; British Institute of Interior Design 2020). In a Textile design context, an intersectional environmentalist posture acknowledges the oppression of women through a historical under-valuing of their labour, lack of voice in leadership and decision-making, and through the capitalist systems of rapid production and consumption that harm both majority-female textile workers and the planet (Mellor 1997; Gale and Kaur 2002).

2.4. Regenerative Design

Regenerative design is an emerging paradigm that seeks to "regenerate rather than deplete underlying life support systems and resources within socio-ecological wholes" (Mang and Reed 2013). It acts as a baseline for the skills future designers will need to support transformational change within the sector. As an emerging design perspective, there are gaps within the literature, particularly with the practical application of regenerative design within the field of Textiles. However, there are a growing number of examples within architecture and the built environment which employ the term 'net-positive' more broadly, thus widening the scope of application (Ichioka 2021). Shifting to regenerative practices does pose a significant challenge to the design sector, which is already struggling to meet less ambitious 'sustainability' targets such as resource efficiency and supply chain transparency (Mang, Haggard and Regenis 2016). To shift all design disciplines to regenerative methods of practice will require transformative change in the sector, and in how we prepare and skill up designers (Wahl 2016). The skills required to work as a regenerative designer are aligned with the 'skills for the future of work', which include creative, critical and systems thinking alongside empathy, citizenship and environmental stewardship (Design Council 2025; World Economic Forum 2025; RSA no date). Regenerative Design is also rooted in place, which shifts the homogenous and global focus of the design industry to the local and the community-based (Wahl 2016).

A regenerative future must also be grounded in post-growth principles that divest from current neoliberal capitalism (Ichioka 2021; Raworth 2017). Even though regenerative activities may appear to have a net positive impact on the planet, they cannot be uncritically pursued within a growth-oriented economic framework (Ichioka 2021; Tsui 2024). This prompts a fundamental question for design practice: must we always build or make something new? Such questioning challenges the very foundations of our profession, as we currently lack a framework for recognizing when not to design (Papaneck 1997). Exercising the ability to refuse creation, acknowledging that some things should not be built or made, requires considerable courage. Emerging economic theories are also questioning the long-term

viability of unchecked capitalism and charting the destructive impact unfettered growth (for some countries and peoples) has had on the planet (Raworth 2017). *Doughnut Economics* theorist and author Kate Raworth proposes alternative economic models, and asks designers to have an active role in shifting mindsets around production and consumption, stating that the first question to be asked in the design process should be 'does it even need to be built?' (Raworth 2017). A necessary uncoupling of design education from extractive industries and patterns of consumption creates space for new, innovative and collaborative pedagogies (Rowe 2025).

3. From Design Frameworks to Design Pedagogy

As these design frameworks are articulated and considered, we now must begin to understand how these frames inspire and shape pedagogical practices. These emerging design frameworks are values-driven, proposing foundational values that are not just applicable to their content, but also to how they are shared and taught. Hence, such design frameworks can be extrapolated into theories of applied pedagogy. The recent report *Rethinking Innovation* reminds us that "a container is only as strong as the values embodied by its creators" (Ledingham 2024). In our case, the container is that of teaching, and to teach regenerative practice is to embody its values. Cardozo, van den Berg, and Wessel, authors of "The Art of Regenerative Educatorship" (2025), a book addressed to educators, present their full selves, through introductory reflections, stories of their lived experiences, genuine interactions between the authors retold on paper, and closing letters (Cardozo 2025; Ledingham 2024). The format of the book itself teaches the reader about regenerative educatorship, and how living by and personifying these values is in and of itself a pedagogy (Cardozo 2025).

A key role of education should be to challenge conventional notions of progress (Ichioka 2021). The idea of progress is often confounded with technological progress in design disciplines and is imaged as a destructive separation from the past, which prevents us from embracing paradigms of care and of nurture for living beings and place (Ichioka 2021). Such values of care and nurture are thought of as feminine in our Western societies (Ichioka 2012; hooks 1994). This reiterates the importance of a textile design pedagogy grounded in feminism, and intersectional environmentalism.

3.1. Critical Pedagogy

Critical pedagogy is an educational and pedagogical strategy that stresses the need for teachers and students to actively transform knowledge together, rather than simply consume it (hooks 1994). At its most ambitious, the overarching aim of critical pedagogy is to educate students on how to lead a meaningful life, how to hold power and authority accountable, and to develop the skills, knowledge and courage to challenge commonly-held assumptions and to advocate for a more socially just world (hooks 1994; Freire 1970). Critical pedagogy asserts that students can engage with their learning through activating their own agency, and in doing so can actively participate in narrating their experiences through a culture of questioning that opens a dialog between their inner and outer worlds, and accepted forms of self- and social-recognition (hooks 1994). They can use the knowledge they gain both to critique the world in which they live, and when necessary to intervene in socially responsible ways to change it (Freire 1970).

Central to critical pedagogy is shifting the burden of ownership from teachers to students, and articulating the assumed relationships between knowledge, authority, and power (Freire 1970; Freire 2021). Giving students the opportunity to be problem-posers and to engage in a culture of questioning in the classroom foregrounds the critical issue of who has control over the conditions of learning and how specific modes of knowledge, identities and authority are constructed within classroom relationships (hooks 1994). Knowledge is not simply received by students but actively transformed and is open to be challenged. Such an active definition of knowledge is an essential step towards agency, self-representation, and regenerative learning (hooks 1994; Damos 2024).

Particularly in the current social and political climate, education and pedagogical methods often serve as strategies of repression and control; students today have never been more highly-monitored and restricted in freedom of thought and expression, from the homogenizing effects of social media to the ability of phones and personal technology to track movements, clicks, and bodily functions (Tsui 2024; hooks 1994). It is more necessary than ever for education to be a bastion of freedom, and to teach students their capacity for breaking free from oppression of action and thought (hooks 1994).

3.2. Regenerative Pedagogy

Regenerative pedagogy and regenerative education have emerged from critical pedagogy, eco-pedagogy and the teachings of Freire (Lyubansky et al. 2022; Misiaszek 2022). As with regenerative design, regenerative pedagogy recognizes the damage of extractive learning models and explores ways to decolonize and nourish students, staff and the learning environment (Damos 2024). It expands beyond formal education and encourages lifelong learning, but for the purpose of our approach, regenerative pedagogy will be explored within the context of a higher education institution (Cardozo 2025). Regenerative pedagogies remain a novel approach in higher education as they draw upon Living Systems Theory aiming to connect educators to themselves, to nature, and to the community and institution around them (Peavy 2024). It breaks with the histories of extraction that have informed design pedagogies and design education in the past, and recognizes the limitations of existing models such as Sustainable Design and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) as a pathway to transformational change (Rowe 2025; Redstrom 2017). More examples of academics and scholars adopting regenerative pedagogy are becoming visible, though not yet undertaken on a large scale (Damos 2024; Freire 1970; Macrine 2009).

Regenerative pedagogies highlight an evolving and iterative response to student needs (Damos 2024). Hence, our proposed pedagogy is student-led and student-forward, and includes methods which propose quick action, even where the established pedagogical 'success' of the practice is not yet watertight. While most academics rely on 'expertise' to inform teaching practice, these emerging frameworks allow for co-learning with students, and allows students agency and voice, not just as stakeholders, but as those with an embodied experience of climate catastrophe (Tsui 2024). Allowing the students to shape and drive the conversation, and then in turn the design of curriculum and their course, creates a space to allow for and support intimate and challenging conversation, to share differing worldviews, and then to take action collectively (Irwin 2015; hooks 1994; Damos 2024).

Regenerative pedagogies must also still support the reality of students entering the current world. The challenge for educators lies in accompanying students as they navigate this terrain, moving through the grief of letting go of anticipated futures, while also embracing the excitement of new possibilities that emerge when disciplinary boundaries are released (Bednarek 2024). Caring for students on this journey must also be grounded in an intersectional approach, acknowledging that many students face structural constraints, need to support their families, and may need to currently engage with capitalism, while still giving them the hope and toolset to action radical acts of systemic change in the future (hooks 1994; Ichioka 2021; Tsui 2024).

4. Proposed Regenerative textile design Framework and Discussion

The development of a framework for Textile design practice and pedagogy based on the above theories must push against and challenge established and existing design and Textile design pedagogies. The field of Textile design is well positioned to unify technical-, textile-, and material-related cultural and environmental practices and to pose deep questions about the role and need for both in a regenerative future.

Our call to develop and formalize a framework has come from ongoing experimentation with emerging pedagogies within our curricula and an institutional push to embed 'sustainability' into all curricula at Loughborough University by 2030. As an exercise to both reflexively examine our own practices and to onboard other enthusiastic colleagues, we are now aiming to formalize and iterate a guiding framework. From this exploration and evaluation of existing pedagogies and design theories, some of the key values that emerge are as follows.

Our proposed regenerative Textile design pedagogy must:

- Recognize students and educators as co-creators of knowledge, working in partnership as changemakers to understand our collective agency, and to consolidate belief in the freedom to identify and action our shared visions for the future.

- Empower students and educators to take steps toward climate justice and to engage in individual and collective reflexive practice, which includes acknowledging that each step taken may not be the 'perfect action' and might not be global in scale.
- Honour, centre, and value the role and wisdom of women and other often-overlooked global majority communities in the historical and contemporary commercial practice of textiles, and to not be held back by limitations placed on the discipline rooted in sexism and gender stereotype.
- Equip students with the agile skills needed for a future textiles industry, which must engage with regenerative design principles to survive and thrive.
- Deepen the connection of humans and more-than-humans to textiles and material, recognize complexity and interconnectedness, and the crucial role placed-based material knowledge, adaptation, and sustainable material literacy will play in systemic healing.
- Making and un-making: have the courage to challenge business (and education) as usual.
- Recognize the importance of personal wellbeing in both students and staff for a flourishing educational ecosystem.

5. Next Steps

Design education must decouple from its origins, or potentially must reclaim them again, as in its purest definition to design is a profoundly human thing; a reflection of the innate desire to "change existing situations into preferred ones" (Simon 1982). However, with the codification of design as a profession came the unfortunate coupling with capital gains and a mostly unchecked exponential growth curve of commercially available goods and services, all while espousing design's role in society as identifying and meeting human needs (Papanek 1995). It's hard to believe that nearly 40 years on from Papanek writing in *Design for the Real World* that "Design, if it is to be ecologically responsible and socially responsive, must be revolutionary and radical", and we are still trying to find ways to embody this ethos (Papanek 1985).

The impending climate collapse has put a sharper point on these conversations, and new theorists and champions are emerging, most notably intersectional feminist and climate justice youth activists, who are speaking to the needs of people and planet from their less-then-rosy lived experiences. Those of us old enough to be working in higher education, old enough to be developing curriculums and theories for pedagogy, are lucky enough to still have memories of unspoiled childhoods and experiences that aren't coloured by the knowledge of an ecological and societal disaster looming on the horizon. The most radical and critical act of a pedagogy must be to first listen to the students and allow them to shape the education and the tools they will

wield in the future. We can no longer straddle a line of perpetuating old ideologies and old ways of design thinking and practice and instead must embrace the uncertainty in the times ahead. Emergent theories and frameworks such as critical pedagogy, regenerative pedagogy, and our own emerging regenerative Textile design pedagogy shift the frame and the role of both students and educators.

The next steps for our proposed framework are to expand our theories into a series of actionable steps and guiding principles. These will now be co-developed with students in a series of stakeholder workshops, as the pedagogy is for us all, and must acknowledge all of our worldviews, aims, areas of expertise, and hopes for our short and long-term futures. These co-creation workshops will engage with a wide range of stakeholders and the resulting *Framework 1.0* will be immediately actioned within our Textile design programme. Feedback will be intentionally and continually gathered and used to inform iterations and adaptations of the pedagogy so that it may continue to meet the needs of the students and those 'teaching'. Our proposed regenerative Textile design pedagogy is not intended to be prescriptive, but rather to be an embodied practice of regenerating ourselves, our teaching, our curriculums, and our futures. And most crucially, as educators we must remember that "to change everything, we need everyone" (Ichioka 2021).

References

- Adamson, Glenn, editor. *The Craft Reader*. Oxford: Berg Publishers, 2010.
- Ball, Linda, Emma Pollard, and Nick Stanley. *Creative Graduates Creative Futures*. Brighton: Institute for Employment Studies and Creative Graduates Creative Futures Higher Education Partnership, 2010.
- Barber, Elizabeth Wayland. *Women's Work: The First 20,000 Years—Women, Cloth, and Society in Early Times*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company, 1995.
- Bednarek, Steffi, ed. *Climate, Psychology and Change: Reimagining Psychotherapy in an Era of Global Disruption and Climate Anxiety*. Berkeley, CA: North Atlantic Books, 2024.
- Bell, Dawne, Hughes, Chris and Owen-Jackson, Gwyneth. 'The (Continuing) Gender Debate' in *Debates in Design and Technology Education*. edited by Gwyneth Owen-Jackson, 153-165. Routledge 2013
- British Institute of Interior Design. "Ground-breaking Diversity Analysis of Interior Design Students in 2020." Accessed October 10, 2025. <https://biid.org.uk/resources/ground-breaking-diversity-analysis-interior-design-students>
- Cardozo, Mieke Lopes, Bas van den Berg, and Koen Wessels, eds. *The Art of Regenerative Educatorship: A Developmental Guide*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2025.
- Clayton, Susan, Christie M. Manning, Kirra Krygsman, and Meighen Speiser. *Mental Health and Our Changing Climate: Impacts, Implications, and Guidance*. Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association and ecoAmerica, 2017.
- Crenshaw, Kimberlé. "Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Colour." *Stanford Law Review* 43, no. 6 (1991): 1241-1299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>.
- Coulter, Janet. "Using E-Textiles to Challenge Gender Perceptions in STEM, Design and Career Aspirations of Secondary School Students." *Journal of textile design Research and Practice* 11 (1-2): (2023) 168-93. [doi:10.1080/20511787.2023.2209960](https://doi.org/10.1080/20511787.2023.2209960).
- Damus, O. "Regenerative and restorative pedagogy: The foundation of a new contract for cognitive justice." *Prospects* 54, 441-449 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-024-09683-y>
- Design Council. *Skills for Planet Blueprint*. Design Council, 2025
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. *A New Textiles Economy: Redesigning Fashion's Future*. 2017. <http://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/publications>
- European Parliament. *The Impact of Textile Production and Waste on the Environment* (Infographic). Brussels: European Parliament, 2021.
- FashionUnited. "Global Fashion Industry Statistics." FashionUnited. Accessed October 10, 2025. <https://fashionunited.com/statistics/global-fashion-industry-statistics>
- Freire, Paulo. *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. Translated by Myra Bergman Ramos. New York: Herder and Herder, 1970.
- Freire, Paulo, and Ana Maria Araújo Freire. *Pedagogy of Hope: Reliving Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. Notes by Ana Maria Araújo Freire. Translated by Robert R. Barr. London: Bloomsbury Publishing, 2021.
- Gale, Colin, and Jasbir Kaur. *The Textile Book*. London: Berg (Bloomsbury), 2002.
- Hickman, Caroline, Elizabeth Marks, Panu Pihkala, Susan Clayton, R. Eric Lewandowski, Elouise E. Mayall, Britt Wray, Catriona Mellor, and Lise van Susteren. "Climate Anxiety in Children and Young People and Their Beliefs about Government Responses to Climate Change: A Global Survey." *The Lancet Planetary Health* 5, no. 12 (2021): e863-e873. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(21\)00278-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00278-3)
- hooks, bell. *Teaching to Transgress: Education as the Practice of Freedom*. New York: Routledge, 1994.
- Hossain, Elahi, Araceli Camargo, and Jake Robinson. *The Planetary Dysregulation: The Physiological Link Between Planetary Dysregulation and Human Health*. Urban Health Council, 2022. <https://www.urbanhealthcouncil.com/reports-playbooks/the-planetary-dysregulation>.
- Ichioka, Sarah, and Michael Pawlyn. *Flourish: Design Paradigms for Our Planetary Emergency*. Axminster: Triarchy Press, 2021.
- Iglesias, Teresa, Ellen Haverhals, and Tatiana De Wée. "The Fashion Industry Needs to Break with Its Gender and Women's Rights Problems." *Fashion Revolution*. Accessed October 10, 2025. <https://www.fashionrevolution.org/the-fashion-industry-needs-to-break-with-its-gender-and-womens-rights-problems/>
- Igoe, Elaine. *textile design Theory in the Making*. London: Bloomsbury Visual Arts, 2021.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Edited by Hans-Otto Pörtner, Debra C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegria, et al. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022. <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/>
- Irwin, Terry. "Transition Design: A Proposal for a New Area of Design Practice, Study, and Research." *Design and Culture* 7, no. 2 (2015): 229-246.
- Irwin, Terry. "The Emerging Transition Design Approach." *Cuadernos del Centro de Estudios de Diseño y Comunicación*, no. 73 (2019).
- Labour Behind the Label. "The Women Who Make Your Clothes." Labour Behind the Label. Accessed October 10, 2025. <https://labourbehindthelabel.org/the-women-who-make-your-clothes/>
- Ledingham, Katie, Sarah Hartley, and Richard Owen. *Rethinking Innovation: Alternative Approaches for People and Planet*. Cham, Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan, 2024.
- Lean, Marion. "Materialising Data Feminism – How textile designers are Using Materials to Explore Data Experience". *Journal of textile design Research and Practice* 9:2, (2021) 184-209
- Lopes Cardozo, Mieke, Bas van den Berg, and Koen Wessels. *The Art of Regenerative Educatorship*. Amsterdam University Press, 2025.
- Lovelock, James E. "Gaia as Seen through the Atmosphere." *Atmospheric Environment* 6, no. 8 (1972): 579-580. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981\(72\)90076-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981(72)90076-5)
- Lyubansky, Mikhail, Giovana Mete, Gillian Ho, Emily Shin, and Yamenah Ambreen. 'Developing a More Restorative Pedagogy: Aligning Restorative Justice Teaching with Restorative Justice Principles'. In *Peace Psychology Book Series*, by Gabriel Velez and Theo Gavrielides. Springer International Publishing, 2022. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-13101-1_5.
- Macrine, Sheila, ed. *Critical Pedagogy in Uncertain Times: Hope and Possibilities*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009.

- Mellor, Mary. *Feminism and Ecology*. New York: New York University Press, 1997.
- Mang, Pamela, and Reed, Bill. 'Regenerative Development and Design'. In *Sustainable Built Environments*, edited by Vivian Loftness and Dagmar Haase. Springer, 2013
- Mang, Pamela, Haggard, Ben and Regenis. *Regenerative Development and Design*. Wiley, 2016.
- Misiaszek, Greg William. 'An Ecopedagogical, Ecolinguistical Reading of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): What We Have Learned from Paulo Freire'. *Educational Philosophy and Theory* 54, no. 13 (2022): 2297–311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2021.2011208>.
- Morlet, A., R. Opsomer, S. Herrmann, L. Balmond, C. Gillet, and L. Fuchs. *A New Textiles Economy: Redesigning Fashion's Future*. Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017.
- Munro, Ealasaid. "Feminism: A Fourth Wave?" *Political Insight* 4, no. 2 (2013): 22–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-9066.12021>.
- Ogunbode, Charles A., et al. "Climate Anxiety, Wellbeing and Pro-Environmental Action: Correlates of Negative Emotional Responses to Climate Change in 32 Countries." *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 84 (2022): 101887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2022.101887>.
- Papanek, Victor. *Design for the Real World: Human Ecology and Social Change*. 2nd ed. London: Thames and Hudson, 1985.
- Papanek, Victor. *The Green Imperative: Ecology and Ethics in Design and Architecture*. London: Thames & Hudson, 1995.
- Parker, Rozsika, and Griselda Pollock. *Old Mistresses: Women, Art, and Ideology*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1981.
- Parker, Rozsika. *The Subversive Stitch: Embroidery and the Making of the Feminine*. London: The Women's Press, 1984.
- Peavy, Kenny. 'Regenerative Education: Teaching and Learning That Heals and Restores'. Medium, 9 September 2024. <https://kennywpeavy.medium.com/regenerative-education-teaching-and-learning-that-heals-and-restores-4c82b445b3d6>.
- Raworth, Kate. *Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st-Century Economist*. White River Junction, VT: Chelsea Green Publishing, 2017.
- Redström, Johan. *Making Design Theory*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2017.
- Rosner, Daniela K. *Critical Fabulations: Reworking the Methods and Margins of Design*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2018.
- Rowe, Aidan 'A Necessary Shift in Design Education: From Outputs to Outcomes'. *International Journal of Art and Design Education* 44, no. 1 (2025): 4-17
- Sachs, Wolfgang, ed. *The Development Dictionary: A Guide to Knowledge as Power*. London: Zed Books, 1992.
- Schwendler, Sônia Fátima, and Lucia Amaranta Thompson. "An Education in Gender and Agroecology in Brazil's Landless Rural Workers' Movement." *Gender and Education* (2016).
- Servant-Miklos, Ginie. *Pedagogies of Collapse: A Hopeful Education for the End of the World as We Know It*. London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2024.
- Simon, Herbert A. *The Sciences of the Artificial*. 2nd ed. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1982.
- Textile Exchange. *Preferred Fiber & Materials Market Report 2021*. 2021. https://textileexchange.org/app/uploads/2021/08/Textile-Exchange-Preferred-Fiber-and-Materials-Market-Report_2021.pdf
- Thomas, Leah. *The Intersectional Environmentalist: How to Dismantle Systems of Oppression to Protect People + Planet*. New York: Voracious, 2022.
- Tsui, Tori. *It's Not Just You*. London: Gallery UK, 2024.
- UNFCCC. *UN Helps Fashion Industry Shift to Low Carbon*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2018. <https://unfccc.int/news/un-helps-fashion-industry-shift-to-low-carbon>
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. *Annual Report: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement*. Bonn: UNFCCC, 2021.
- Wahl, Daniel Christian. *Designing Regenerative Cultures*. Triarchy Press, 2016
- World Economic Forum. *Future of Jobs Report 2025*. World Economic Forum, 2025. <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-future-of-jobs-report-2025/>.
- World Health Organization. *Mental Health and Climate Change: Policy Brief*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2022. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/351720>